

Investigations on homo- and hetero-leptic isopropoxometallates of lead(II)[†]

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Abstract : Novel homo- and hetero-leptic isopropoxometallates of lead(II) of the types $\{[Zr_2(OPr^i)_9]Pb(\mu-F)_2\}_2$ (1a), $\{[Nb(OPr^i)_6]Pb(\mu-F)_2\}_2$ (1b), $\{[Al(OPr^i)_4]Pb(\mu-F)_2\}_2$ (1c), $\{[Sn_2(OPr^i)_9]Pb(\mu-F)_2\}_2$ (1d), $[Pb\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}_2]$ (1e), $[Pb\{Nb(OPr^i)_6\}_2]$ (1f), $[Pb\{Al(OPr^i)_4\}_2]$ (1g) and $[Pb\{Sn_2(OPr^i)_9\}_2]$ (1h) have been prepared for the first time by interactions of PbF_2 and the appropriate potassium isopropoxometallate in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio. Fluoro-derivatives 1a, 1b and 1c undergo fluoride-alkoxide or isopropoxometallate exchange reactions to yield derivatives of the types $\{[Zr_2(OPr^i)_9]Pb(\mu-OR)_2\}_2$ (R = Prⁱ (2a), Bu^t (2b)), $\{[Nb(OPr^i)_6]Pb(\mu-OPr^i)_2\}_2$ (2c), $\{[Al(OPr^i)_4]Pb(\mu-OPr^i)_2\}_2$ (2d), $[Zr_2(OPr^i)_9]Pb\{Al(OPr^i)_4\}$ (2e), $[Sn_2(OPr^i)_9]Pb\{Zn_2(OPr^i)_9\}$ (2f), $[Nb(OPr^i)_6]Pb\{Ta(OPr^i)_6\}$ (2g), $[Al(OPr^i)_4]Pb\{Nb(OPr^i)_6\}$ (2h) and $[Al(OPr^i)_4]Pb\{Sn_2(OPr^i)_9\}$ (2i). Characterization of new complexes is mainly based on elemental/isopropoxo group analyses, molecular weight measurements, IR and multinuclear (¹H, ¹³C, ¹⁹F, ²⁷Al and ²⁰⁷Pb) NMR spectral studies.

Keywords : Lead(II) derivatives, lead(II) isopropoxometallates, heterometallic isopropoxides.

Introduction

Lead(II) alkoxide chemistry has so far been centered around simple¹⁻³ and oxo-alkoxide^{3,4} derivatives. Examples of heterometallic alkoxides of lead(II) appear to be limited to $[Pb\{Sb(OR)_4\}_2]$ ⁵, $[Pb\{Ge(OBu^t)_3\}_2]$ ⁶, $[Pb\{Sn(OBu^t)_3\}_2]$ ⁶, $[Pb_6Nb_4O_4(OEt)_{24}]$ ⁴, $[Tl(\mu-OBu^t)_3Pb]^6$, $[(OC)_4Fe.M(\mu-OBu^t)_3Pb(\mu-OBu^t)_3M.Fe(CO)_4]$ ⁷ (M = Sn, Ge), $[Pb(\mu-OBu^t)_3Mn(\mu-OBu^t)_3Pb]^8$, $[Pb_2Ti_2O(OAc)_2(OPr^i)_8]$ ⁹, $[PbTi_2O(OAc)(OEt)_7]$ ⁹, $[PbZr_3O(OAc)_2(OPr^i)_{10}]$ ⁹, $[Pb_2Zn_2(OAc)_4(OPr^i)_4]$ ¹⁰.

In this paper, we report the synthesis and characterization of some novel alkoxometallate derivatives of lead(II). The isolation of such derivatives assumes special significance in view of (i) the susceptibility of lead(II) alkoxides for conversion into oxo-alkoxo species^{3,11-13}, (ii) heterometallic alkoxides and oxo-alkoxides as intermediates in chemical routes to mixed metal oxides⁹, (iii) the use of mixed-metal lead oxides as ceramic¹⁴ and superconducting materials¹⁵ and (iv) the presence of zirconium and lead as key components of the ferroelectric oxides $Pb(Zr,Ti)O_3$ and $(Pb,La)(Zr,Ti)O_3$, which have large potential for applications in infrared detectors^{16a},

non-volatile computer memories^{16b,c} and many electrooptical ceramics^{16d}.

Results and discussion

The reactions of PbF_2 with appropriate potassium isopropoxometallates in 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 molar ratios yield novel heterobimetallic derivatives of lead(II) as illustrated by the following general reaction (eq. 1) :

	n	M	x	y
(1a)	1	Zr	2	9
(1b)	1	Nb	1	6
(1c)	1	Al	1	4
(1d)	1	Sn	2	9
(1e)	2	Zr	2	9
(1f)	2	Nb	1	6
(1g)	2	Al	1	4
(1h)	2	Sn	2	9

[†]Dedicated in loving memory of Professor R. C. Mehrotra (16.2.1922-11.7.2004) former President of the Indian Chemical Society, on occasion of his 6th death anniversary.

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	M	x	y	L
(2a)	Zr	2	9	OPr ⁱ
(2b)	Zr	2	9	OBu ^t
(2c)	Nb	1	6	OPr ⁱ
(2d)	Al	1	4	OPr ⁱ
(2e)	Zr	2	9	Al(OPr ⁱ) ₄
(2f)	Zr	2	9	Sn ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉
(2g)	Nb	1	6	Ta(OPr ⁱ) ₆
(2h)	Al	1	4	Nb(OPr ⁱ) ₆
(2i)	Al	1	4	Sn ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉

All these hetero (bi or tri) metallic alkoxides are extremely moisture sensitive, colourless solids or viscous products, soluble in organic solvents (e.g. C₆H₆, CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂, PhMe, etc.). On ageing, these derivatives tend to attain a yellowish tinge and become less soluble. Ebullioscopic molecular weight measurements in benzene indicate dimeric nature for the derivatives **1a-d** and **2a-d**, while derivatives **1e-h** and **2e-i** are monomeric. They tend to decompose at 160–230 °C even when heated under reduced (10⁻¹ Torr) pressure.

Spectroscopic studies :

Structurally characteristic infrared absorptions¹⁷ are observed in the regions (cm⁻¹) : 1175–1100v (*gem*-dimethyl skeletal vibrations); 1060–940v (C–O) terminal and bridging; 750–675v (Al–O); 640–530v (Zr–O)/(Nb–O); 570–490v (Pb–O).

The ¹H NMR spectra of the new complexes are deceptively simple in most of the cases. For example, in a number of cases, in spite of the possibility of existence of isopropoxy groups in more than one environment only one doublet due to the *gem*-dimethyl protons for the derivatives **1a**, **1e**, **1g** and **2d** in the region δ 1.05–1.45 and one septet due to methine protons for the derivatives **1e**, **1d**, **1f**, **1g**, **1h**, **2b**, **2e** and **2i** have been observed in the region δ 4.05–4.90. Derivatives **1b**, **1c**, **2a**, **2b**, **2e** and **2g** exhibit two doublets for *gem*-dimethyl protons in the region δ 1.05–1.45. Methine protons for the derivatives **1a**, **1b**, **1e**, **2a**, **2b** and **2g** appear as two septets in the region δ 1.00–5.00.

Interestingly, ¹H NMR spectrum of the derivative **2f** exhibited peaks at δ 1.07, 1.15, 1.18, 1.23 and 1.29 prob-

ably arising from three doublets due to methyl protons of terminal and bridging isopropoxy groups. The methine protons are observed as only two septets at δ 4.07 and 4.67 respectively.

The ¹³C NMR spectra of a few selected derivatives such as **1c**, **2b**, **2e** and **2f** exhibit three signals in the regions δ 63.71–70.47 and 27.03–28.76 respectively for α- and β-carbons of isopropoxy groups. For derivatives **1a**, **1b**, **1d**, **1e**, **1f**, **1g** and **1h** four signals in the regions δ 63.70–78.06 and 24.80–28.70 have been observed, respectively due to α- and β-carbons of isopropoxy groups. These data are generally in agreement with the observed ¹H NMR peaks with a slight variation in a few cases.

The fluoro-complexes **1a**, **1b** and **1c** exhibit sharp ¹⁹F NMR resonances at δ -135.4, -129.79, -168.30 respectively.

The ²⁷Al NMR spectra of the derivatives **1c**, **1f**, **2e**, **2f**, **2d** show broad absorptions centered in the region δ 44.0–77.0, characteristic of tetracoordinated aluminium species¹⁸.

In spite of an adequate natural abundance of 20% and a value of *I* = ½, the ²⁰⁷Pb NMR studies on heterometallic alkoxides are of only recent origin^{3,9,11,12}. During the course of the present studies, ²⁰⁷Pb NMR measurements have been carried out to throw light on the structural features of the newly synthesized derivatives.

The observed ²⁰⁷Pb NMR chemical shifts for the derivatives **1a**, **1d**, **2a**, **2e** and **2i** in the range δ 1950–2500 tend to indicate a six-coordination⁹ environment around lead(II) involving tetradentate ligation of {Zr₂(OPrⁱ)₉}⁻ or {Sn₂(OPrⁱ)₉}⁻ moieties and bidentate nature of {Al(OPrⁱ)₄}⁻ (in **2e** and **2i**) as has been recently established by the X-ray crystal structures of [{Ba{Zr₂(OPrⁱ)₉}(μ-OPrⁱ)₂}]¹⁹, [Ba{Zr₂(OPrⁱ)₉}]¹⁹ and [Cd{Zr₂(OPrⁱ)₉}(μ-Cl)]₂²⁰.

The spectrum of **1c** exhibits ²⁰⁷Pb NMR signal of δ 3107.93, which is interpretable in terms of a tetrahedral^{3,11,12} environment around lead(II) according to the formulation [{(PrⁱO)₂Al(μ-OPrⁱ)₂Pb(μ-F)}]₂ if allowance is made for higher electronegativity of fluorine.

Although in the absence of X-ray crystallographic evidence these exploratory physicochemical data are insufficient to indicate definitive structures for the new complexes, yet these data tentatively support the following structural formulations :

$[\{\eta^4\text{-}[\text{M}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9]\}\text{Pb}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ (M = Zr (**2e**), Sn (**2i**)),

$[(\text{Pr}^i\text{O})_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Pb}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ (**1g**),

$[(\text{Pr}^i\text{O})_4\text{Nb}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Pb}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Nb}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]$ (**1f**),

$[\{\eta^3\text{-}[\text{M}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9]\}\text{Pb}\{\eta^3\text{-}[\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9]\}]$ (M = Zr (**1e**), M = Sn (**2f**), M, Zr = Sn, Sn (**1h**)).

Experimental

Rigorous precautions were taken throughout to exclude moisture from solvents, reactants and glassware.

Lead(II) fluoride was prepared by interaction of lead(II) acetate and potassium fluoride in aqueous medium followed by repeated washing of the solid product (PbF_2) with $\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}/n\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{14}$ and drying under reduced pressure (0.1 mm Hg) at 100 °C. Found : Pb, 84.4. Calcd. for PbF_2 : Pb, 84.5%. $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ ^{21,22}, $\text{Zr}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\cdot\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ ^{21,23} and $\text{Nb}(\text{OPr}^i)_5$ ^{21,24} were prepared by the literature methods.

In Pb/Al heterobimetallic alkoxides, lead was estimated as PbSO_4 and aluminium in the filtrate was estimated as oxinate¹⁸. In case of niobium containing bi- or ter-metallic derivatives, niobium was precipitated as hydrated pentoxide ($\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_5\cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$)²⁵ and estimated as Nb_2O_5 prior to the separation and estimation of lead as lead sulphate²⁵. Zirconium in zirconium containing hetero (bi- or tri-) metallic derivatives was precipitated as mandelate²⁵ and estimated as oxide ZrO_2 after initial removal of lead as PbSO_4 . Isopropoxy contents were estimated by an oxidimetric method^{22a}.

IR (4000–200 cm^{-1}) spectra were recorded as Nujol mulls on a CARL ZEISS JENA specord M-80 spectrophotometer. Multinuclear (¹H, ¹³C, ²⁷Al, ¹⁹F, ²⁰⁷Pb) NMR spectra were recorded on JEOL FX90Q spectrometer. ¹H (89.55 MHz) and ¹³C (22.49 MHz) chemical shifts were referenced to internal SiMe_4 . The ¹⁹F (84.90 MHz), ²⁷Al (23.29 MHz) and ²⁰⁷Pb (54.44 MHz) chemical shifts were measured with reference to external C_6F_6 , aqueous $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, respectively. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in benzene using a thermistor sensing device.

(a) Preparation of $K\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}$:

A solution of KOPr^i [prepared by the reaction of potassium (4.93 g, 125.83 mgatom) and isopropyl alcohol (~ 15 ml) in benzene (~ 20 ml)] was added dropwise to a benzene (~ 30 ml) solution of SnCl_4 (7.29 g, 27.98 mmol) at 0 °C. After the addition was complete, the resulting

reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h. The precipitated KCl (8.54 g, 114.54 mmol) was removed by filtration. Removal of volatiles from the filtrate under reduced pressure afforded $\text{KSn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9$ as a white foamy solid (11.14 g, 98%). Found : Sn, 29.3; OPr^i , 56.6. Calcd. for $\text{KSn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9$: Sn, 29.40; OPr^i , 56.8%.

(b) Preparation of heterobimetallic derivatives of lead(II) :

In view of similarities in synthetic procedures, only details of some typical preparations are being described below :

(i) $[\{\text{Pb}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}(\mu\text{-F})\}_2]$ (**1c**) :

To a prestirred suspension of freshly prepared PbF_2 (3.07 g, 12.52 mmol) in benzene (25 ml) was added dropwise a solution of $\text{KAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ {obtained by the reaction of potassium (0.49 g, 12.53 mgatom) with isopropyl alcohol (5 ml) and $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ (2.56 g, 12.53 mmol) in benzene (15 ml) and isopropyl alcohol (10 ml)}. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 72 h, followed by refluxing for 2 h to ensure completion of the reaction. After filtration of the precipitated KF (0.71 g, 12.22 mmol), the removal of volatiles from the filtrate afforded the title complex (5.88 g, 95%) as a colourless viscous mass. The product (**1c**) in 45% yield was obtained by recrystallization at -10 °C from *n*-hexane/dichloromethane mixture. Found : Pb, 42.2; Al, 5.4; OPr^i , 48.0; M.W. 980. Calcd. for $\text{FPb}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}$ (**1c**) : Pb, 42.3; Al, 5.5; OPr^i , 48.3%; M.W. 490.

In a similar procedure, reaction of PbF_2 (1.17 g, 4.77 mmol) with $\text{KNb}(\text{OPr}^i)_6$ (2.32 g, 4.77 mmol) afforded a product of composition $\text{FPb}\{\text{Nb}(\text{OPr}^i)_6\}$ (**1b**), which could be recrystallized at -10 °C from *n*-hexane/toluene mixture as a pale yellow soft solid in 50% yield. Found : Pb, 30.5; Nb, 13.7; OPr^i , 52.1; M.W. 1379. Calcd. for $\text{FPb}\{\text{Nb}(\text{OPr}^i)_6\}$ (**1b**) : Pb, 30.8; Nb, 13.8; OPr^i , 52.6%; M.W. 674.

(ii) $[\{\text{Pb}\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}(\mu\text{-F})\}_2]$ (**1a**) :

The above procedure involving the equimolar reaction of PbF_2 with $\text{KZr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9$ in benzene-isopropyl alcohol did not work as $[\{\text{Zr}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\cdot\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}\}_2]$ tends to crystallize out of the solution. However, this difficulty was overcome by the exclusion of free Pr^iOH in the reaction mixture.

The modified procedure involved the reaction of PbF_2 (2.87 g, 11.74 mgatom) and solid $\text{KZr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9$ {prepared by the reaction of potassium (0.46 g, 11.76 mgatom),

isopropyl alcohol (5 ml) and $Zr(OPr^i)_4 \cdot Pr^iOH$ (9.07 g, 11.75 mmol), followed by the removal of volatiles} in benzene (30 ml) and stirring the reaction mixture at room temperature for 72 h. The precipitated KF (0.65 g, 11.18 mmol) was removed by filtration. Removal of volatiles from filtrate yielded the title product (**1a**) (9.93 g, 90%) as a white soft solid, which was recrystallized from a (3 : 1) mixture of $n-C_6H_{14}/CH_2Cl_2$ at $-10^\circ C$ in 60% yield. Found : Pb, 22.0; Zr, 19.6; OPr^i , 56.2; M.W. (ebullioscopically in benzene) 1845. Calcd. for $FPb\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}$ (**1a**) : Pb, 22.0; Zr, 19.4; OPr^i , 56.6%; M.W. 941.

Adopting a similar procedure for equimolar reaction of PbF_2 (1.27 g, 5.18 mmol) with $KSn_2(OPr^i)_9$ (4.18 g, 5.18 mmol) in benzene afforded $\{[Pb\{Sn_2(OPr^i)_9\}(\mu-F)]_2\}$ (**1d**) in 95% yield, which was recrystallized from n -hexane/toluene mixture at $-10^\circ C$ as a pale yellow solid (**1d**) in 60% yield. Found : Pb, 20.6; Sn, 23.8; OPr^i , 53.1; M.W. 2013. Calcd. for $FPb\{Sn_2(OPr^i)_9\}$: Pb, 20.8; Sn, 23.9, OPr^i , 53.4%; M.W. 995.

(iii) Preparation of $\{[Pb\{Al(OPr^i)_4\}(\mu-OPr^i)]_2\}$ (**2d**) :

To a benzene (~ 20 ml) solution of **1c** (2.83 g, 5.79 mmol) a suspension of $KOPr^i$ in benzene (~ 15 ml) {prepared by the reaction of potassium (0.23 g, 5.80 mgatom) with isopropyl alcohol (~ 5 ml)} was added slowly. The reaction mixture was stirred at $50^\circ C$ for 24 h. The precipitated potassium fluoride (0.31 g, 5.33 mmol) was removed by filtration. Removal of the volatiles under reduced pressure (1 mm Hg) at room temperature yielded **2d** (2.93 g 95%) as a colourless pasty mass, which was recrystallized from a (3 : 1) mixture of $n-C_6H_{14}/CH_2Cl_2$ at $-10^\circ C$ as a colourless solid (yield 50%). Found : Pb, 38.9; Al, 5.0; OPr^i , 55.4; M.W. 1100. Calcd. for $Pb\{Al(OPr^i)_4\}(OPr^i)$ (**2d**) : Pb, 39.1; Al, 5.1; OPr^i , 55.8%, M.W. 530.

2c was also prepared according to the same method from **1b** and $KOPr^i$.

(iv) Preparation of $\{[Pb\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}(\mu-OPr^i)]_2\}$ (**2a**) :

A suspension of $KOPr^i$ {prepared by reacting potassium (0.07 g, 1.79 mgatom) with isopropyl alcohol (10 ml) followed by removal of volatiles} in benzene (20 ml) was added, slowly to a benzene (20 ml) solution of **1a** (1.68 g, 1.77 mmol). After the addition of $KOPr^i$ was complete the reaction mixture was initially stirred at room temperature for 24 h, followed by stirring at $50^\circ C$ for 12 h. The precipitated KF (0.09 g, 1.51 mmol) was removed by filtration. The volatiles were removed from the filtrate

to yield **2a** (1.70 g, 98%) as a colourless viscous product, which solidifies slowly on ageing and could be recrystallized from n -hexane/toluene mixture at $-15^\circ C$ in 45% yield. Found : Pb, 21.1; Zr, 18.5; OPr^i , 59.9; M.W. (ebullioscopically in benzene) 2013. Calcd. for $(Pr^iO)Pb\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}$ (**2a**) : Pb, 21.1; Zr, 18.6; OPr^i , 60.3%; M.W. 981.

Following an analogous procedure reaction of **1a** (1.77 g, 1.88 mmol) with $KOBu^t$ (0.21 g, 1.89 mmol) in benzene yielded the product **2b** (1.79 g, 96%) as a colourless glassy material. Found : Pb, 20.6; Zr, 18.3; OPr^i , 53.3; M.W. 1970. Calcd. for $(Bu^tO)Pb\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}$ (**2b**) : Pb, 20.8; Zr, 18.3, OPr^i , 54.0%; M.W. 995.

(v) Preparation of $[Pb\{Sn_2(OPr^i)_9\}_2]$ (**1h**) :

A benzene (30 ml) solution of $KSn_2(OPr^i)_9$ (6.13 g, 7.57 mmol) was added slowly to a prestirred (~ 24 h) suspension of PbF_2 (0.93 g, 3.79 mmol) in benzene (20 ml). The resulting reaction mixture was stirred for 48 h at room temperature, followed by stirring at $50^\circ C$ for 24 h. The precipitated KF (0.42 g, 7.23 mmol) was removed by filtration and volatiles from the filtrate were removed under reduced pressure (1 mm Hg) to afford **1h** (6.24 g, 97%) as a pale yellow sticky solid. The product was recrystallized from n -hexane/dichloromethane mixture at $-10^\circ C$ in 50% yield. Found : Pb, 11.8; Sn, 27.1; OPr^i , 60.7; M.W. 1821. Calcd. for $[Pb\{Sn_2(OPr^i)_9\}_2]$ (**1h**) : Pb, 11.9; Sn, 27.2; OPr^i , 60.9%, M.W. 1746.

Analogously the following complexes were also obtained :

1e : [From PbF_2 (0.98 g, 3.99 mmol) and $KZr_2(OPr^i)_9$ (6.03 g, 7.99 mmol)]. Colourless solid. Recrystallized from n -hexane/dichloromethane at $-15^\circ C$ in 45% yield. Found : Pb, 12.4; Zr, 22.5; OPr^i , 64.5; M.W. 1506. Calcd. for $[Pb\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}_2]$: Pb, 12.7; Zr, 22.3; OPr^i , 65.0%; M.W. 453.

1f : [Prepared from PbF_2 (1.37 g 7.06 mmol) and $KNb(OPr^i)_6$ (6.86 g, 14.11 mmol)]. Pale yellow soft solid. Recrystallized from $n-C_6H_{14}/PhMe$ mixture at $-15^\circ C$ in 65% yield. Found : Pb, 18.6; Nb, 16.8; OPr^i , 64.0; M.W. 1090. Calcd. for $[Pb\{Nb(OPr^i)_6\}_2]$: Pb, 18.8; Nb, 16.9; OPr^i , 64.3%; M.W. 1102.

1g : [Prepared from PbF_2 (2.78 g, 11.33 mmol) and $KAl(OPr^i)_4$ (6.86 g, 22.66 mmol)]. Colourless solid. Recrystallized in 65% yield from a mixture of n -hexane and isopropyl alcohol at $-10^\circ C$. Found : Pb, 28.0; Al, 7.3; OPr^i , 64.1; M.W. 757. Calcd. for $[Pb\{Al(OPr^i)_4\}_2]$: Pb, 28.2; Al, 7.4; OPr^i , 64.4%; M.W. 734.

(c) *Typical procedure for the synthesis of heterotrimetallic isopropoxides of lead(II) (2e, 2f, 2g, 2h, 2i) :*

(i) *Preparation of $[\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}Pb\{Sn_2(OPr^i)_9\}]$ (2f) :*

To a mixture of $FPb\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}$ (3.20 g, 3.40 mmol) and $KSn_2(OPr^i)_9$ (2.75 g, 3.40 mmol) 50 ml of benzene was added. The mixture was initially stirred at room temperature for 48 h and then at 50 °C for 24 h. The precipitated KF (0.17 g, 3.01 mmol) was separated by filtration and volatiles from the filtrate were removed under reduced pressure (1 mm Hg) at 25 °C to afford the title complex (2f) as a pale yellow soft solid. Recrystallization from toluene/chloroform mixture at -15 °C yielded analytically pure product (2f) in 60% yield. Found : Pb, 12.2; Zr, 10.7; Sn, 13.9; OPrⁱ, 62.5; M.W. 1744. Calcd. for $[\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}Pb\{Sn_2(OPr^i)_9\}]$: Pb, 12.3; Zr, 10.8; Sn, 14.0; OPrⁱ, 62.9%, M.W. 1691.

Following complexes were prepared analogously from appropriate heterobimetallic lead(II) derivatives and a potassium isopropoxometallate :

2e : [Prepared from **1c** (4.3 g, 8.78 mmol) and $KZr_2(OPr^i)_9$ (6.6 g, 8.76 mmol)]. White soft solid. Recrystallized from *n*-hexane/chloroform mixture at -15 °C in 50% yield. Found : Pb, 17.4; Al, 2.2; Zr, 15.5; OPrⁱ, 64.2; M.W. 1200. Calcd. for $[\{Al(OPr^i)_4\}Pb\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}]$: Pb, 17.5; Al, 2.3; Zr, 15.4; OPrⁱ, 64.8%; M.W. 1185.

2i : [From **1c** (2.99 g, 6.11 mmol) and $KSn_2(OPr^i)_9$ (4.93 g, 6.10 mmol)]. Pale yellow solid, which could be recrystallized in 55% yield from a mixture of *n*-hexane/dichloromethane at -10 °C. Found : Pb, 16.6; Sn, 19.2; Al, 2.1; OPrⁱ, 61.5; M.W. 1263. Calcd. for $[\{Al(OPr^i)_4\}Pb\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}]$: Pb, 16.7; Sn, 19.1; Al, 2.2; OPrⁱ, 62.0%; M.W. 1240.

(ii) *Preparation of $[\{Nb(OPr^i)_6\}Pb\{Ta(OPr^i)_6\}]$ (2g) :*

The suspension of $KTa(OPr^i)_6$ [prepared by the reaction of potassium (0.14 g, 3.66 mgatom), isopropyl alcohol (5 ml) and $Ta(OPr^i)_5$ (1.76 g, 3.68 mmol) in benzene (20 ml) under refluxing conditions, followed by removal of volatiles] in benzene (25 ml) was added to a benzene (25 ml) solution of **1b** (2.47 g, 3.67 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 48 h, followed by stirring at 50 °C for 24 h. Filtration of KF (0.19 g, 3.27 mmol) gave colourless solution which was evacuated to dryness. Recrystallization of the resulting white solid from *n*-C₆H₁₄/CH₂Cl₂ at -10 °C afforded **2g** as a white soft solid in 50% yield. Found : Pb, 17.3; (Nb+Ta), 29.6; OPrⁱ, 59; M.W. 1200. Calcd. for

$[\{Nb(OPr^i)_6\}Pb\{Ta(OPr^i)_6\}]$: Pb, 17.4; (Nb+Ta), 29.7; OPrⁱ, 59.5%; M.W. 1190.

The complex $[\{Al(OPr^i)_4\}Pb\{Nb(OPr^i)_6\}]$ (**2h**) was prepared in a similar manner from **1c** (2.67 g, 5.95 mmol) and $KNb(OPr^i)_6$ (2.66 g, 5.46 mmol) and was recrystallized from dichloromethane at -15 °C to afford a white soft solid in 40% yield. Found : Pb, 22.2; Al, 2.9; Nb, 10.1; OPrⁱ, 64.0; M.W. 1002. Calcd for $[\{Al(OPr^i)_4\}Pb\{Nb(OPr^i)_6\}]$: Pb, 22.6; Al, 2.9; Nb, 10.1; OPrⁱ, 64.4%; M.W. 918.

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